

Theoretical study on relations between the helix structure and optical rotation of alanine

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Abstract : Seven possible pairs (R and S) of alanine conformers, both in the gaseous phase and in the aqueous solution, have been optimized at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p). And in the aqueous phase the polarizable continuum model has been used in the optimization. The geometry parameters have been discussed in details. The optical rotations of all the conformers have been calculated using B3LYP method of density functional theory at the basis sets of 6-311++G(2d,2p) and aug-cc-pvdz. The relations between the optical rotations and helical structures in the molecule conformers have been discussed theoretically, and arrived at a conclusion that just the helical structure in the molecule has made the chiral molecule have the property of the optical rotation.

Keywords : Helix structure, optical rotation, alanine conformers.

The optical activity of chiral organic molecules was discovered nearly 200 years ago, and the phenomenon receives a wide use in characterizing those compounds. Because of the chiral nature of the building blocks of living matters, optical phenomena associated with the chirality constitute an important topic in physical chemistry. The lowest-order phenomenon in the transparent region is a natural optical activity, that is, the optical rotation of the polarization plane of a linearly polarized light after transmission through a sample of chiral molecules. The specific optical rotation, a parameter characterizing the natural optical activity, depends strongly on the conformation of the molecule¹⁻⁴ and is therefore in principle a sensitive tool for structural investigations. However, this sensitivity makes the correlation between the optical rotation and the electronic and geometrical structure a difficult task. Even for a rigid molecule, a seemingly small perturbation such as changing the solvent may be beyond the extent of reversing the sign of the rotation^{5,6}. A number of attempts have been made to gain an understanding of the phenomenon. Some have made use of empirical models such as Brewster's rules⁷ and the quadrant and octant rules⁸. Theoretical simulations, where

one can concentrate only on one particular factor influencing a given property, are therefore invaluable in developing an understanding of the different factors that influence an observed optical rotation. The study of optical rotations by theoretical calculations is a young field, but now interest in it is increasing rapidly. The first *ab initio* calculations were reported in 1997⁹. And recently, due to the enormous advance in computer power and algorithmic development, more and more people have become interested in the study of the optical rotations using the quantum chemistry calculation. Pecul^{10,11} have studied the conformation dependence of the optical rotation of the amino acid (alanine, proline, serine and cysteine). However, optical rotation calculations are very sensitive to the computational method and also the basis set that we select in computation¹². Stephens *et al.*¹³ showed that the B3LYP-correlated hybrid functional combined with suitable large basis sets yielded reliable results for rigid systems. So in calculations of the specific optical rotation, the size of the basis set converges at aug-cc-pvdz and 6-311++G(2d,2p).

One of the fundamental issues of chemistry is the relationship between the property of a molecule and its

structure. Chemists have long sought the principle governing this fundamental relation with impressive successes in a wide range of chemical problems. This close relationship between the reaction and molecular structure is especially important for biomolecules. Indeed, the structure of biomolecule can be considered as the blueprint of the underlying mechanism of life itself.

Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins. And alanine is the smallest chiral amino acid of the roughly 21 amino acids common in nature. It is simply an amino group and a carboxyl group separated by a chiral carbon, which is usually chosen as a good model for studying biological systems exhibiting the bonding type of amino acids. Until recently, many studies about alanine have been reported : In Csaszar's¹⁴ report 13 conformers were determined from *ab initio* calculation. And Alonso had studied the jet-cooled rotational spectrum of neutral alanine using laser-ablation molecular-beam Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy (LA-MB-FTMW)¹⁵. And also there are some other report about it¹⁶⁻¹⁸, however, there are very few reports on the study about its optical rotation, and only Pecul¹⁰ has studied the conformational effects on the optical rotation in the gaseous phase. In fact, a significant amount of alanine in the environmental is present in the aqueous phase. And Pecul has mentioned that it has very large influence on the conformation and optical rotation of the aqueous environment.

Few of these studies have addressed the question of exactly how the structures make the chiral molecules to be optically active. Our interest in the phenomenon has led us to examine several aspects of the overall problem. The theoretical calculations usually refer to the gaseous phase, but here we want to calculate the optical rotations of all the conformers in aqueous solutions. This allows a better comparison of the theory and experiment and also provides a reference point for studies of solvent effects on optical rotations.

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the dependence of the optical rotation of alanine on the conformation both in the gaseous phase and aqueous solution using density functional theory, and in the aqueous solution in order to take the water solvent effect into account we have optimized all the conformers of alanine using the polarizable continuum model (PCM). And we also want to do some study on what has exactly caused the chiral molecules with the properties of the optical activities.

Theory and computational details :

Recently, density functional theory (DFT) has been

accepted by the *ab initio* quantum chemistry as a cost-effective approach for the computation of the molecular structure and other properties. Use of the B3LYP functional with sufficiently large basis sets may open the way to reliable studies on related medium-sized biomolecules, e.g. oligopeptides and their analogues¹⁴. It is not only much less expensive than the conventional electron corrections methods, but it also can provide many properties comparable in accuracy to experimental values and those obtained using MP2 methods or even higher level *ab initio* methods. Therefore, we have optimized the structures of alanine conformers in the aqueous phase using the polarizable continuum model at the basis set of 6-311++G(2d,2p).

Here we have calculated the specific optical rotation values at a wavelength of 589.3 nm. That is just the frequency of the yellow sodium D-line which is always used for experimental measurements. The purpose of the paper is to compare the results with the experiments' in future. The theory about the calculations of optical rotations here is as follows¹⁹⁻²², and the dipole-magnetic dipole-polarizable tensor is given by the expression :

$$G'_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{-4\pi}{h} \sum_{n \neq s} \frac{\omega}{\omega_{ns}^2 - \omega^2} \times \text{Im} \{ \langle \Psi_s^0 | \bar{\mu}_\alpha | \Psi_n^0 \rangle \langle \Psi_n^0 | \bar{m}_\beta | \Psi_s^0 \rangle \} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\mu}_\alpha$ and \bar{m}_β are the electric dipole moment and magnetic dipole moment operators respectively, while Ψ_s^0 and Ψ_n^0 represent the ground and excited electronic state wave-functions, respectively; $\omega_{ns} = 2\pi(E_n^0 - E_n^s)/h$, where E_n^0 and E_n^s are the unperturbed energies of states n and s , respectively; and ω is the angular frequency of the exciting radiation. It is useful to define the quantity :

$$\beta = -\omega^{-1} (G'_{xx} + G'_{yy} + G'_{zz}) / 3 \quad (2)$$

which is related to the optical rotation ϕ (in radians/cm) as

$$\phi = 4\pi N \beta \omega^2 (n^2 + 2) / 3 c^2 \quad (3)$$

where N represents the number of molecules per unit volume, and n is the refractive index of the medium and $\omega^{-1} G'_{\alpha\alpha}$ is in CGS units. The experimental optical rotations are most commonly reported as the specific rotation $[\alpha]$ in units of $\text{deg}[\text{dm}(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)]^{-1}$. The corresponding theo-

retical quantity is $[\alpha] = 3600\phi V_m/2\pi M$, where M and V_m are the molar mass and molar volume. By using these definitions, a convenient expression for the specific rotation is given as

$$[\alpha] = 0.1343 \times 10^{-3} \beta \bar{\nu}^2 (n^2 + 2) / 3M \quad (4)$$

with the units : β is in (bohr)⁴, M in g/mol and $\bar{\nu}$ (wave number at which the optical rotation is measured) in cm⁻¹.

All the computations have been performed using Gaussian03 program package²³.

Results and discussion

Selected geometric parameters, including bond lengths and bond angles of the seven pairs (R and S) of alanine conformers both in the gaseous phase and in the aqueous solution are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, and the conformers are shown in Fig. 1. In Table 3 and Table 4, we give out some dihedral angles of the conformers of alanine in the gaseous phase and aqueous solution. In Table 5 we give out the energies of the conformers in gas phase. In Table 6 and Table 7 the specific optical rotation values $[\alpha]$ and the rotation parameters β at the wavelength of 589.3 nm of the seven pairs of alanine conformers both

in the gaseous phase and aqueous solution are listed out.

Geometries and energies :

By doing enough geometric optimization we have obtained seven pairs (R and S) of alanine stationary conformers, and the structures of the alanine conformers in the gaseous phase at B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p) level are shown in Fig. 1, and the most interesting structure parameters including bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles are listed in Table 1 and Table 3. Inspecting the data shown in Table 1 we can find that the bond lengths and bond angles of each pair are the same, while the dihedral angles, as listed in Table 3, have the same value but just in the opposite signs.

Surveying the bond angles of the seven pairs of alanine conformers listed in Table 1, we can find that the deviations among the seven pairs are larger than those of the bond lengths. The largest deviation among all the conformers is the A_{C2C1N5}, which is up to 5.5 degrees, and the others are no more than 4.7 degrees.

In the aqueous solution, in order to take the water solvent effect into account, we have optimized all the conformers using the polarizable continuum model at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p) and all

Table 1. Selected geometric parameters (Par.) of the seven pairs (R and S) of alanine conformers (Con.)

Con. \ Par.	R _{C1C2}	R _{C2C3}	R _{C1N5}	R _{C3O6}	R _{C3O7}	A _{C2C1C3}	A _{O6C3O7}	A _{C2C2N5}
R1/S1	1.528	1.544	1.475	1.202	1.340	111.12	122.82	114.82
R2/S2	1.532	1.528	1.461	1.204	1.358	109.36	122.21	110.10
R3/S3	1.536	1.538	1.453	1.198	1.361	109.32	119.88	109.86
R4/S4	1.542	1.528	1.456	1.198	1.357	108.75	120.17	114.71
R5/S5	1.541	1.519	1.464	1.203	1.385	108.92	122.52	115.46
R6/S6	1.522	1.523	1.467	1.202	1.357	111.28	122.29	110.54
R7/S7	1.543	1.517	1.458	1.204	1.353	108.58	122.73	115.16

The units here : bond lengths (R) in angstrom (Å) and the bond angles (A) in degree.

Table 2. Selected geometric parameters (Par.) of the seven pairs (R and S) of alanine conformers (Con.) in the solvent phase

Con. \ Par.	R _{C1C2}	R _{C2C3}	R _{C1N5}	R _{C3O6}	R _{C3O7}	A _{C2C1C3}	A _{O6C3O7}	A _{C2C2N5}
R1/S1	1.529	1.536	1.469	1.213	1.332	111.55	121.63	110.28
R2/S2	1.533	1.528	1.461	1.215	1.338	108.97	122.78	110.28
R3/S3	1.535	1.534	1.457	1.211	1.343	108.31	119.03	110.20
R4/S4	1.543	1.523	1.462	1.210	1.342	108.32	119.19	114.81
R5/S5	1.542	1.520	1.466	1.210	1.337	108.72	122.92	114.93
R6/S6	1.523	1.523	1.471	1.213	1.339	111.62	122.68	110.45
R7/S7	1.543	1.518	1.462	1.213	1.340	108.69	122.94	114.95

The units here : bond lengths (R) in angstrom (Å) and the bond angles (A) in degree.

the obtained interesting geometric parameters, bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles of seven pairs

Fig. 1. The optimized seven possible pairs of alanine conformers in the gaseous phase at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p).

of alanine conformers are shown in Table 2 and Table 4. By inspecting the data listed in Table 2, we have found that the bond lengths and bond angles for each pair are just the same. While for the dihedral angles of each pair, their signs are just opposite to each other and their absolute values are not as listed in Table 2, because there are some deviations to each other. The largest deviations are in the dihedral angle $D_{C_2C_1C_3O_7}$ of pairs R6 and S6, which is only 3.34 degree (161.772 to 165.117). From that we can conclude that the solvent effect has some influence, but not very much, on the structures of the alanine conformers.

The energies of all the conformers both in gaseous phase and in PCM model were optimized at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p) and B3LYP/6-311++G**. In our calculation, each pair of the enantiomers has the same energies. In Table 5, the total energies of the gaseous phase R conformers at the computational

Table 3. Some mainly selected dihedral angles (D, unit in degree) of the seven pairs (R and S)

Con.	D	$D_{C_2C_1C_3O_6}$	$D_{C_2C_1C_3O_7}$	$D_{O_6C_3C_1N_5}$	$D_{O_7C_3C_1N_5}$
R1		-41.988	139.728	-170.030	11.687
S1		41.988	-139.728	170.030	-11.687
R2		-100.012	79.115	135.428	-45.445
S2		100.012	-79.115	-135.428	45.445
R3		101.908	-76.883	21.087	160.122
S3		-101.908	76.883	-21.087	-160.122
R4		96.148	-81.154	-29.164	153.534
S4		-96.148	81.154	29.164	-153.134
R5		92.936	84.245	139.380	-43.438
S5		-92.936	-84.245	-139.380	43.438
R6		-13.939	168.582	-136.463	46.058
S6		13.939	-168.582	136.463	-46.058
R7		97.557	-80.134	-28.117	154.137
S7		-97.557	80.134	28.117	-154.137

Table 4. Some mainly selected dihedral angles (D, unit in degree) of the seven pairs (R and S) in solvent phase

Con.	D	D _{C2C1C3O6}	D _{C2C1C3O7}	D _{O6C3C1N5}	D _{O7C3C1N5}
R1		-44.419	137.764	-172.031	9.753
S1		-44.092	-137.669	172.090	-9.767
R2		-95.066	83.646	140.297	-40.990
S2		96.756	-82.047	-138.657	42.538
R3		88.359	-89.601	-34.367	147.673
S3		-88.414	-89.562	34.317	-147.706
R4		88.333	-88.511	-37.159	145.997
S4		-87.609	89.065	37.631	145.494
R5		-90.745	86.707	1441.924	-40.623
S5		90.464	-87.011	-142.198	40.336
R6		-21.038	161.772	-144.419	38.391
S6		17.426	-165.117	140.591	-41.951
R7		99.885	-77.947	-26.406	155.761
S7		-99.679	78.148	26.576	-155.596

level of B3LYP/6-311++G** were shown so as to compare with the Csaszar's¹⁴ results.

As shown in Table 5, the energy of the conformer R1 (S1) at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G** corresponded to the Csaszar's conformer II. And in the conformer R1, the COOH group adopts a *trans* configuration, correspond to the Bianco's¹⁵ conformer IIa in some degree, and the same type of intramolecular hydrogen bond with the IIa's, as shown in Fig. 4, can be found in the conformer R1.

The corresponding relation in the energy of the rest conformers (R2-R7) in this paper and Csaszar's are also shown in Table 5. There are some deviations: R5 and R6 in this paper, which correspond to the Csaszar's VB and VA all have their own enantiomorphous isomers, while VA and VB are enantiomers in Csaszar's result. In our opinions, the energy barrier between VA and VB (-303.852920 and -303.852492) is too large in some degree.

The main purpose of this paper is to investigate the optical rotation of the alanine conformer, so the *meso* conformers are not mentioned here.

Specific optical rotations :

The relation between the molecule structure and its optical rotation is the evidence that the material's property is determined by its structure. Different conformers should have different values of optical rotations. For this reason, we have calculated the optical rotations of all the conformers. The goal of this work is to investigate that how the chiral structures of alanine affect the optical rotation of each conformer. And here we also want to discuss the relation between the optical rotations and the chiral molecular structures.

The specific optical rotation values at 589.3 nm calculated using density functional theory (B3LYP) at the basis sets of 6-311++g(2d,2p) and aug-cc-pvdz of all the seven pairs of alanine conformers both in the gaseous phase and aqueous solution are listed in Table 6 and Table 7.

As can be seen the data in Table 6 and Table 7, the results of B3LYP method at the basis set of 6-311++G(2d,2p) have some deviation with the results of the basis set of aug-cc-pvdz. This has just confirmed that as

Table 6. The specific optical rotation (OR) values ($[\alpha]$) and rotation parameters (β) at a wave length of 589.3 nm

Con.	OR	B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p)		B3LYP/aug-cc-pvdz	
		$[\alpha]$	β	$[\alpha]$	β
R1		-36.28	-0.0836	-27.92	-0.0644
S1		36.28	0.0836	27.92	0.0644
R2		124.93	0.2880	122.21	0.2817
S2		-124.92	-0.2880	-122.21	-0.2817
R3		58.15	0.1340	48.77	0.1124
S3		-58.14	-0.1340	-48.77	-0.1124
R4		16.32	0.0367	12.81	0.0295
S4		-16.32	-0.0367	-12.81	-0.0295
R5		33.80	0.0779	20.38	0.0470
S5		-33.80	-0.0779	-20.38	-0.0470
R6		33.34	0.0769	38.51	0.0888
S6		-33.34	-0.0769	-38.51	-0.0888
R7		46.31	0.1067	36.22	0.0835
S7		-46.31	-0.1067	-36.22	-0.0835

The units are deg $[\text{dm}(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)]^{-1}$.

Table 5. The total energies of gaseous R conformers (C denotes conformers and M denote method, unit in Hartree)

M	C							
	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	
B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p)	-323.8668	-323.8654	-323.8588	-323.8571	-323.8635	-323.8639	-323.8652	
B3LYP/6-311++G**	-323.8560	-323.8544	-323.8469	-323.8450	-323.8524	-323.8529	-323.8539	
Csaszar's	II	III	VI	VIII	VB	VA	IV	

Table 7. The specific optical rotation (OR) values ($[\alpha]$) and rotation parameters (β) of alanine in solvent phase

Con.	B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p)		B3LYP/aug-cc-pvdz	
	$[\alpha]$	β	$[\alpha]$	β
R1	-44.85	-0.1034	-37.14	-0.0856
S1	44.83	0.1033	37.06	-0.0854
R2	132.06	0.3044	131.07	0.3021
S2	-131.30	-0.3026	-130.13	-0.2999
R3	76.85	0.1771	72.09	0.1662
S3	-77.51	-0.1787	-72.72	-0.1676
R4	70.03	0.1614	57.08	0.1332
S4	-70.76	-0.1631	-58.87	-0.1357
R5	31.38	0.0723	15.54	0.0358
S5	-31.44	-0.0725	-15.40	-0.0517
R6	32.71	0.0754	35.86	0.0827
S6	-26.26	-0.0605	-30.58	-0.0705
R7	32.71	0.1452	41.02	0.0945
S7	-26.06	-0.1456	-41.24	-0.0951

The units are $\text{deg} [\text{dm}(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)]^{-1}$.

mentioned in the section of the introduction, the computation of the optical rotation is very sensitive to the computation method. But all the specific optical rotation values obtained at different basis sets for one pair are in the same sign. This phenomenon can confirm the reliability of our calculation in some degrees.

Table 6 gives the calculated results of optical rotations and the parameters of the seven pairs of alanine conformers in the gaseous phase. After inspecting it we can find that for one pair (R and S), the optical rotation value $[\alpha]$ and rotation parameter β have the same absolute values, but they have just the opposite signs. After we have surveyed the data listed in Table 6, the optical rotations and rotation parameters of the seven pairs of the alanine conformers in the aqueous solution optimized using the polarizable continuum model, we can find that $[\alpha]$ and β for one pair (R and S) still have the opposite signs, and more importantly, not like the results of the conformers in the gaseous phase, their absolute values of just one pair also have some deviations to each other. Take the results of the basis set aug-cc-pvdz for example, the largest deviation of the absolute values of the rotation is between the results R6 and S6, and the specific optical rotation $[\alpha]$ of R6 is 35.86, with the parameter $\beta = 0.0827$, while the specific optical rotation $[\alpha]$ of S6 is -30.58, with the parameter $\beta = -0.0705$, so the deviation of absolute value $[\alpha]$ is up to 5.28.

Why do the chiral molecules' R conformers and S

conformers have the just optical rotations, and why can the specific optical rotations of conformer pairs (R and S) of alanine in the gaseous phase have the same absolute values while in the aqueous solution can not? Here we just want to have some discussion on these questions.

We know that the materials' properties should be determined by the structures and so should be the optical rotations of chiral molecules. As mentioned above, the relation between the optical rotation and chiral molecules is the evidence of that. And we know that the structure of a molecule should be reflected by the structure parameters. So then we do some inspection on the geometric parameters.

As discussed in the geometry discussion section, the parameters, the bond lengths and bond angles of R alanine conformers and S conformers both in the gaseous phase and the aqueous solution, have the same values with each other, which can be easily found in surveying the data listed in Table 1 and Table 2.

The dihedral angles of the seven pairs (R and S) of conformers : in the gaseous phase, just as shown in Table 3, have the same absolute values but the signs are opposite to each other, just as the specific optical rotations $[\alpha]$ and rotation parameter β of the gaseous phase conformer; in the aqueous solution, as discussed in the section of geometry, for each pair of R and S, their signs are opposite to each other and the absolute values of R conformer and S conformer have some deviations, though not very much, just as the specific optical rotations values $[\alpha]$ and rotation parameter β of the aqueous conformer.

From this point of view we can conclude that the dihedral angles of the chiral molecule conformers influence their optical rotations, as Pecul^{10,11} reported. And here we take conformer R1 for example, the affect of the change of the dihedral angle $D_{C2C1C3O6}$ on the optical rotation has also been calculated in this work, and the results have been shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen from it, the change of the dihedral angle has a great effect on the optical rotation of the molecule.

How does this influence come about? Why the chiral molecules have the properties of the optical rotation.

In the year of 1882, Gibbs²⁴ had pointed out that when electrons were restricted in the helical routeway, the left helical conductor will show left optical rotations while the right will show right rotations. Tinoco and Freeman²⁵ had carried out an experiment of the helices of brass wires, and the result of it proved that the brass wire helices have the properties of optical rotation.

Fig. 2. The affection of the change of dihedral angle $D_{C2C1C3O6}$ on the optical rotations of conformer R1 at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p).

The formula and procedures to define the helix mentioned here is as follows :

First, the molecule structure optimization, through optimizing the structure to obtain the conformer with the minimum energy.

Second, the formation of the helical line, join the chemical bond, bonding atom or radical on the framework linking a molecule, along the directions that incline to the formation of the annular closed curve and with the shortest distances to form the helical line. Just as the given demonstration²⁶ in Fig. 3.

Third, the definition of the helicoids, the plane that formed of one circle of helical line is the helicoid.

Fourth, the definition of the helix axis : The helix axis should pass through the center of all the helicoids and be perpendicular to them.

Fifth, the definition of the direction of the helical line : Observed along the direction of the helical line forward, which is the direction going along the helix axis and

Fig. 3. A given demonstration of helix in alanine molecule.

being far away from the observer, if the helical line is anticlockwise, it will be a left-rotation helix, while the opposite will be right-rotation helix.

Now let us do some study on the structure of the conformers of the seven pairs of alanine. For one pair of conformers of alanine, R or S, they all have the properties of the optical rotation. As we have discussed above, there should be helical structure in the molecule. Just as the demonstration of the helix structure in the molecule of alanine given in Fig. 3. If R has right (plus) optical rotation, it will have right helix in its molecule, just as shown in Fig. 3. When it become left-rotation conformer, for the reason that the geometry parameters changed, just as dihedral angles, all the sign of them have become opposite. So the helix in the molecule will become a left one. As a result of this, its optical rotation will change too. From this point of view, we conclude that just the diversification in the dihedral angles makes different conformers with different helical structures, so as to the optical rotations, and in another words, just the change of the helix structure in chiral molecules makes their optical rotations different from each other.

Fig. 4. The demonstration of the hydrogen bond in R1.

And someone may ask that why some molecular conformer which have helix structures in their conformer, but do not have the properties of optical rotations ? We know that there are two types of helix structures : right and left. Once the affection of the right one just can counteract that of the left one, the properties of optical rotations will disappear. The reason for most chiral molecules with the property of optical rotation is that one type of helix (right or left) may play a dominant role to the other one.

However, we know that the results of the optical rotation value obtained by using the theoretical calculations still have deviations from the results obtained by measuring in the experiments. This is because the result of the calculation is only the specific optical rotation value of

one single conformer, while the result of the experiment should be the result of a combination of the contributions from different conformers and alanine in aqueous solutions will become zwitterion. As a result of this, here we just want to do some predictions theoretically and we know that the study of the optical properties of chiral molecules using the method of the theoretical chemistry calculation still needs a lot of work to do for us.

Conclusions :

Seven possible pairs (R and S) of alanine conformers, both in the gaseous phase and aqueous solution at the computational level of B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,2p), have been optimized. And in the aqueous phase the polarizable continuum model has been used in the optimization, while the geometric parameters has been discussed in details and the optical rotations of all the conformers have been calculated using B3LYP method of density functional theory at the basis sets of 6-311++G(2d,2p) and aug-cc-pvdz. The relation between the optical rotations and the helical structures in the molecule conformers has been discussed theoretically, and arrived at a conclusion that just the helical structure in the molecule makes the chiral molecule have the property of optical rotation.

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